

**Occurrence of Two New Esters of
6 β -Hydroxyloganin in *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis*†**

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WE have reported earlier two new iridoid glucosides arbortristoside A and B from the seeds of *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* and both of them were found to have anticancer activity against methyl

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cholanthrene induced fibrosarcoma^{1,2}. The other iridoids reported from the seeds are nyctanthoside³, 6 β -hydroxyloganin and its 6-*p*-coumaroyl ester⁴. The leaves of this plant have been used in traditional medicine for the treatment of various diseases like chronic fevers, rheumatism and intestinal worm infections. The leaf extract is reported to have antiinflammatory and antimalarial activities^{5,6}. Hence we took up the chemical investigation of the leaves of this plant in search of its active principles.

Earlier workers reported the isolation of mannitol, β -amyrin, β -sitosterol, hentriacontane, benzoic acid⁷, astragalin, nicotiflorin⁸, oleanolic acid, nyctanthic acid, friedelin and lupeol⁹ from the leaves. In this paper we report the isolation and characterisation of a mixture of two new esters of 6 β -hydroxyloganin **1** and **2** from the leaves.

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected. ¹H nmr spectra were recorded on a Bruker AM 300 L Supercon spectrometer at 300.13 MHz relative to TMS. ¹³C nmr was run at 75.5 MHz. Standard procedures were used for nmr experiments. The leaves of *N. arbor-tristis* were collected from Madras, India in August 1988. A voucher specimen has been deposited at the herbarium of this Institute under the registry no. 701.

Isolation: Coarsely powdered leaves (3 kg) were extracted with hexane, EtOAc and EtOH successively at room temperature. EtOAc extract was dried and subjected to column chromatography over silica gel (500 g). Elution with EtOAc yielded a gum in good yield, which was rechromatographed on silica gel. The EtOAc eluate yielded a mixture of iridoids **1** and **2** as an amorphous hygroscopic powder. The EtOH extract was evaporated to dryness under reduced pressure, treated with F₂O and extracted with Et₂O, EtOAc and *n*-BuOH. The EtOAc-soluble fraction on column chromatography over silica gel yielded more of the above mixture on elution with EtOAc (1.5 g), [α]_D -65° (*c*=2, EtOH); ν_{\max} (KBr) 3 400, 2 910, 1 710, 1 630, 1 450, 1 280, 1 080, 870, 770 and 720 cm⁻¹; λ_{\max} (EtOH) 224.5, 232sh and 270.6 nm; ¹H nmr and ¹³C nmr data in Tables 1 and 2 respectively.

Acetylation of iridoids 1 and 2: The mixture of iridoids (**1** and **2**; 150 mg) was refluxed with Ac₂O (3 ml) and freshly fused NaOAc in an oil-bath for 4 h. Work-up in the usual way afforded the pentaacetates (120 mg), m.p. 80°.

Acid hydrolysis of iridoids 1 and 2: The mixture of iridoids (**1** and **2**; 150 mg) was dissolved in EtOH (7 ml) and was refluxed with 6*N* aqueous HCl (1.5 ml) for 2 h. The reaction mixture was worked up in the usual way and the sugar was identified as D-glucose by paper chromatography.

Alkaline hydrolysis of iridoids 1 and 2: The mixture of iridoids (**1** and **2**; 250 mg) was treated with 0.5 *N* NaOH (2.5 ml) and heated on a water-

TABLE 1—¹H NMR SPECTRAL DATA (300.13 MHz)

H	1 and 2 (CD ₃ OD)	Arbortristoside A (CD ₃ OD)
1	5.35 d, <i>J</i> 4.4 Hz	5.3 d, <i>J</i> 3 Hz
3	7.55 s	7.46 s
5	3.02 m	3.0 t, <i>J</i> 6 Hz
6	4.11 m	4.07 t, <i>J</i> 4.5 Hz
7	5.2 t (5.4 t)	5.16 t
8	2.24 m	2.2 m
9	2.24 m	2.2 m
10	1.06 d, <i>J</i> 6.8 Hz	1.03 d, <i>J</i> 6 Hz
12	3.67 s	3.68 s
1'	4.65	4.6 d, <i>J</i> 6.2 Hz
2'	3.15	3.15 dd, <i>J</i> 6.2, 6.3 Hz
3'	3.27	3.15 dd, <i>J</i> 6.3, 9.3 Hz
4'	3.2	3.2 t, <i>J</i> 9.3 Hz
5'	3.3	3.3 dd, <i>J</i> 3.3, 9 Hz
6'	3.65, 3.85 d, <i>J</i> 9.3 Hz	3.65 dd, <i>J</i> 3.3, 9.3 Hz 3.85 d, <i>J</i> 9.3 Hz
α^b	6.55 AB q, <i>J</i> 16 Hz	6.41 AB q, <i>J</i> 15.1 Hz
β^b	7.7 AB q, <i>J</i> 16 Hz	7.7 AB q, <i>J</i> 15.1 Hz
2'', 6''	7.6 (8.03, d, <i>J</i> 7.4 Hz)	7.52 d, <i>J</i> 6.3 Hz
3'', 5''	7.3 (7.4)	6.9 d, <i>J</i> 6.3 Hz
4''	7.4 (7.6)	—
OMe	—	3.77 s

^aValues in parenthesis are the chemical shifts for **2**; other shifts are common for both **1** and **2**. ^b α and β proton shifts are for arbortristoside A and **1** only.

TABLE 2—¹³C NMR SPECTRAL DATA (75.5 MHz)

C	1 and 2 ^a (CD ₃ OD)	Arbortristoside A (CD ₃ OD)
1	98.3	18.2
3	154.7	154.7
4	111.0	110.9
5	40.1 (40.3)	40.1
6	79.5 (79.6)	79.4
7	78.5 (78.9)	78.2
8	37.9 (38.0)	37.9
9	46.5	46.5
10	15.3	15.5
11	170.6 (170.7)	170.6
12	52.6	52.6
1'	100.6 (100.7)	100.6
2'	75.2	75.2
3'	78.8	78.9
4'	72.1	72.1
5'	78.5	78.5
6'	63.3	63.3
CO	168.9 (168.4)	169.4
α^b	119.4	116.6
β^b	146.9	148.9
1''	136.3 (129.9)	128.9
2'', 6''	130.5 ^c (131.1 ^c)	131.5
3'', 5''	130.0 ^d (129.7 ^d)	116.0
4''	131.9 (134.7)	163.7
OMe	—	56.4

^aValues in parenthesis are chemical shifts for **2**; other shifts are common for both **1** and **2**. ^b α and β carbon shifts for arbortristoside A and **1** only. ^{c,d}Assignments interchangeable.

bath for 3 min. The solution was then acidified with 1*N* HCl and extracted with Et₂O and *n*-BuOH successively. The Et₂O extract on column chromatography over silica gel yielded benzoic acid (30 mg, m.p. 122°) and *trans*-cinnamic acid (20 mg, m.p. 132–33°), and were found to be identical with authentic samples.

The BuOH extract was evaporated under reduced pressure and was taken up in MeOH. The solution was then treated with an ethereal solution of CH_2N_2 at 0° . The mixture after usual work-up and purification through a silica gel column yielded a crystalline material, m.p. 222° , which was identified as 6β -hydroxyloganin by extensive homodecoupling studies and by comparison with an authentic sample (m.p., m.m.p. and tlc).

Results and Discussion

Ethyl acetate extract of the leaves on chromatography over silica gel yielded a substance as an amorphous hygroscopic powder. Preliminary examination of its spectroscopic data indicated it to be a mixture of two iridoid glucosides whose structures have been completely elaborated and discussed in sequel. The ir spectrum showed bands at 3400 (hydroxyls), 1710 (α,β -unsaturated ester) and 1630 cm^{-1} (olefinic bond). Its uv spectrum showed bands at 224.5, 232sh and 279.6, which indicated the presence of benzoyl and cinnamoyl ester chromophores. Acid hydrolysis of the material afforded D-glucose and alkaline hydrolysis yielded benzoic and cinnamic acids and another acid which on methylation gave 6β -hydroxyloganin. The mass spectrum of the original material had peaks at m/z 148, 147, 131 (cinnamoyl ester), 122, 121, 105, 77 (benzoyl ester) and at 139 (typical of iridoids having a 4-carbomethoxy group¹⁰). A mixture of penta-acetates was formed indicating the presence of one free hydroxyl group in the iridoid skeleton. The ^1H and ^{13}C nmr spectra of the amorphous powder and its penta-acetates showed them to be a mixture of two glucosides **1** and **2** in the ratio of 2 : 3 with traces of diester. The glucosides **1** and **2** could not be separated by chromatography either on a long column of silica gel or on silica gel impregnated with silver nitrate. Attempts to separate them as their acetates were also not successful. There are many examples of compounds isolated as mixtures in the literature, viz. *Opulus* iridoids I, II, III and IV from *Viburnum opulus*¹¹. Though the iridoids **1** and **2** could not be separated, ^1H , ^{13}C , ^{13}C (DEPT) and 2D hetero and homo-correlated nmr spectroscopy allowed the complete assignment of all the protons and carbons in **1** and **2**. Comparison of the spectral data with those of arbortristoside A and B indicated that the iridoids **1** and **2** had the same structural features as arbortristoside A and differed only in the nature of the aryl ester group (Tables 1 and 2). An AB quartet at δ 6.55 and 7.7 (AB q, J 16 Hz) for *trans*-olefinic protons and a 2H doublet at δ 8.03 (d, J 7.4 Hz) for $2''$ - and $6''$ -protons of benzoyl group in the ^1H nmr spectrum of the mixture showed the presence of *trans*-cinnamoyl and benzoyl ester groups. The overlapped methyl doublets at δ 1.06 (J 6.8 Hz) allowed the placement of a methyl group at position-8 as in arbortristoside A. The multiplet at δ 4.11 could be assigned for the proton attached to the carbon carrying the hydroxyl group and the triplets at δ 5.2

and 5.4 for the proton attached to the carbon bearing the aryl ester group in the iridoids **1** and **2**, respectively.

The hydroxyl and aryl ester groups were placed at positions 6 and 7 respectively from the coupling networks observed in the 2D COSY ($^1\text{H}-^1\text{H}$) spectrum. Cross-peaks were observed between the methyl doublet at δ 1.06 (d, H-10) and the multiplet at 2.24 (m, H-8,9). The latter signal was further coupled to the multiplet at 3.02 (H-5). The multiplet at 3.02 showed correlation to the signal at 4.11 which confirmed the presence of hydroxyl at C-6. The aryl ester group was therefore linked to the remaining carbon, C-7. The multiplet at δ 4.11 showed further correlation to the signal at δ 4.9 (C-6 hydroxyl and glucose hydroxyl protons) which was coupled to the proton resonances at δ 3.2–3.3 (glucose carbinyl protons) and CH_3 of solvent at δ 3.25. All the sugar protons could be assigned from the couplings observed between the glucose carbinyl protons. Correlation signals between δ 3.85 and 3.65 indicated them for the $-\text{CH}_2\text{OH}$ of glucose. The δ 3.65 signal was correlating with a signal at 3.3 (H-5'). The signal for the anomeric proton (H-1') at δ 4.65 showed correlation with a signal at δ 3.15 (H-2'). Correlations between the AB quartets at δ 6.55 (cinnamoyl α -H) and 7.70 (cinnamoyl β -H), aromatic proton signals at δ 7.3 and 7.6 and the signals at δ 7.4 and 8.03 were also observable. The carbon shift assignments and the remaining proton assignments followed from 2D hetero-correlated ($^{13}\text{C}-^1\text{H}$) spectral analysis. The triplets at δ 5.2 and 5.4 could be assigned for the H-7 proton in **1** and **2** having *trans*-cinnamoyl and benzoyl ester groups respectively at C-7. From the C-H shift correlated spectrum, 78.5 and 78.9 ppm were assigned for C-7 in **1** and **2** respectively. The signals at 136.3 and 129.9 ppm were assigned for C-1'' of cinnamoyl and benzoyl carbons from ^{13}C (DEPT) nmr spectrum. Their signal intensities were in the ratio of 2 : 3 which showed that the iridoids **1** and **2** were present approximately in the ratio of 2 : 3 in the mixture. Even for the carbons whose chemical shifts were the same for both **1** and **2**, the overlapped signal intensities were in the ratio of 2 : 3. The constancy of the carbon shifts for the glucose showed them to be β -D-glucosides.

The presence of the aryl ester group at position-7 in the iridoids **1** and **2** prompted us to reinvestigate the structure of arbortristoside A isolated from the seeds of this plant. Proton decoupling studies on arbortristoside A showed the presence of *p*-methoxycinnamoyl group at C-7¹² and not at position-6 as reported earlier¹.

The iridoids **1** and **2** have *trans*-cinnamoyl and benzoyl ester groups respectively at C-7 instead of *p*-methoxycinnamoyl ester group in arbortristoside A (**3**). The iridoids **1** and **2** are the aryl esters of 6β -hydroxyloganin.

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